

Evaluation of Clinical Outcomes and Prognostic Factors in Children Suffering from Trauma, Hospitalized in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU): A Review Study

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Abstract:

Trauma is one of the most important causes of mortality in children and, is mentioned as a major public health problem. According to studies, the consequences of trauma in children are potentially less known.

Introduction:

This review study was performed to evaluate the clinical manifestations and prognostic factors regarding children affected by trauma, admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU).

Methodology:

This study is a conceptual review. The steps performed are:

1. Formulating a research question.
2. Searching and extracting research-related studies
3. Selecting related studies.
4. Tabulating and summarizing information and data.
5. Reporting results and conclusions.

Results:

Prognostic factors and clinical manifestations may include acute coagulation caused by trauma, GCS, INR (international normal ratio), fever, demographic and clinical factors, radiological and biological features, pre-hospitalization hypoxia, young age, non-accidental trauma, seizures, subdural hemorrhage and anticonvulsant drugs, neuroimaging and the results in the first and second stages, pupil reaction, arterial hypertension, gender, age, mechanism of injury, pattern of injury, admission time (Order to admit), severity of injuries,

initial CT findings, circulatory disorders, intracranial pressure (ICP, cerebral hypertension (CPP)), infant mortality rate (PIM2), serum lactate, subarachnoid hemorrhage, hypotension, type of trauma, type of lesion, hyperglycemia, primary post-traumatic seizure, early diagnosis and the treatment of life-threatening cases, high ICP, hypertension, AIS, ISS¹, TRISS², PTS, AST and ALT, thrombocytopenia, functional status standard score (FSS³).

Keywords: Trauma, Children, Clinical features, Prognosis

Abstract.

Trauma is the leading cause of death and disability in children. About one in a six children in the United States need emergency care treatment, and more than 10,000 children die from their injuries every year (1). In Iran, trauma is the third leading cause of death and the most important cause of disability in children (2). Trauma is recognized as a major public health concern and is root of child mortality in high-income countries (4, 3) According to studies, all societies with different economical statuses have been facing the issue (5) as it affects all races and cultures, all economic and social statuses are vulnerable to its disastrous effects. But the differences in the mechanism of development, the ways of taking care, and the outcomes, are observed in different communities (6). Every year, about 12,000 children lose their lives following trauma and millions of people suffer from temporary disability. This imposes a substantial financial burden on the community health system.

There are various forms of trauma found in children. One of the most common and fatal traumas is known to be the brain trauma. Brain injury is the most common cause of death and acquired disability among children and young people in developed countries. Even with appropriate and suitable treatment, it is usually accompanied by the neurological disorders (8) and may lead to hypoxia and cerebral ischemia, with secondary brain injury being the leading cause of death in hospital after brain injury (10, 9). Thus, the outcome of head trauma in children varies depending on the availability of the neurosurgical facilities and qualified specialists (11). Head trauma accounts for 40% of deaths (12). In contrast, intrathoracic and the abdominal injuries are the least common cause of death in children, the reason is the causes are less associated with the hypovolemic shock (13). However, according to studies, the consequences of trauma in children are potentially less known (14). For example, high blood sugar is a negative predictive value in children with trauma, severe head trauma, and multiple trauma (15). However, many other trauma assessment systems, such as ISS and RTS have developed, however, none of these marking systems account for its effect on the outcome (16).

Meanwhile, the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) is one of the most important units in any pediatric hospital. Studies show that more than 10,000 children are admitted to the PICU⁴ each year for a variety of reasons (17). About 15% of all pediatric ICU admissions are related to child trauma (18).

Due to the higher rate of trauma in children, the importance of the intense care, and the need of knowledge of the prognostic factors and clinical signs for pediatric trauma is noteworthy, though there is a significant difference in the results of existing studies and the multiplicity of prognostic factors of clinical features in pediatric trauma, therefore Study to evaluate the

¹ injury severity score

² trauma score— injury severity score

³ Functional Status Scale

⁴Pediatric Intensive Care Unit

clinical features and prognostic factors in children with trauma admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU); is done in the form of a review study.

Methodology:

This study is a conceptual review. The steps performed are:

1- Formulating a research question, 2- Searching and extracting research-related studies, 3- Selecting related studies, 4- Tabulating and summarizing information and data, and 5- Reporting results.

2. Search and extraction of research-related studies:

First, articles were searched by the researchers, who first extracted related keywords using the MeSH strategy. Search for resources using the keywords trauma, children, clinical features, prognosis, pediatric intensive care unit in the Persian databases Barekat, Iran Medex, Irandoc, Magiran, SID and using the English keywords Trauma, children, clinical features, prognosis, Pediatric Intensive Care Unit in Google Scholar, Scopus, Science Direct, PubMed, web of science databases from 2000 to 2021 in October and November 2021 was conducted. The words were used separately and also as a combination of two words in the form of phrase, and were searched together using Boolean operators. In order to increase the validity of the study findings, to control the bias in data entry, and the search process, selection of studies and decision-making on entering or constructing the study and evaluation of the full text of the articles was performed by two independent browsers and was overseen by a third party.

Inclusion criteria include all the articles that have examined the full text of the robotic surgery and is available and written in Persian and English. Exclusion criteria were studies unrelated to the title.

3- Inclusive criteria based article collection

Using the above keywords at the end of the search, including 445 articles from Persian databases and 4710 articles from international databases and a total of 5165 studies was collected. The studies were reviewed based on inclusion criteria. The selection of related studies was done in a way that a list of titles and abstracts of all the articles in databases was prepared by the researchers at first. If after reading the title and abstract, it seemed impossible to make a decision about the study, the full text was studied. Then the related articles were independently entered into the research process and eventually 24 articles were included in the study.

4- Tabulation and summarization of data:

At this stage, after the information has been extracted, all the data will be summarized in the relevant tables based on the name of the first author, year, country, title, tools or research elements

Writer	Year	Country	Title	Type of study	Research Tool	Findings
Seuss	2007	USA	Clinical features of associated fever, minor outcomes in children with severe brain injury.	Cross-sectional, Descriptive	Questionnaire	Fever seems to be a major symptom in children suffering from brain trauma. Treatment or even prevention of fever for patients may improve patient outcomes. Because children with head trauma often have unpredictable manifestations, determining future prospects in clinical settings is somewhat inevitable.
Bahlol	2007	Tunisia	Severe Head Injury in Children, Prognostic factors and results.	Cross-Sectional and descriptive.	Questionnaire	The analysis shows the pediatric trauma score (PTS ⁵) was low at the admission, the injury severity score (ISS ⁶) was high, or the pediatric mortality risk score (PRISM ⁷) was also high, meningeal shock, bleeding, or bilateral mydriasis, and serum glucose > 10 mmol / L was associated

⁵ Pediatric Trauma Score

⁶ Injury Severity Score

⁷ Pediatric risk of mortality (PRISM)

						with mortality. Multivariate analysis showed that the factors with poor prognosis included PRISM > 20 and bilateral mydriasis at the time of admission. Head injury is one of the most common causes of hospitalization and is often followed by road accidents. The short-term prognosis is poor, associated with a high mortality rate (24.3%), and influenced by demographic, clinical, radiological, and biological factors.
Aoki	2019	Japan	Epidemiology, treatment patterns, and mortality in pediatric trauma patients in Japan.	Cross-Sectional, Descriptive.	Questionnaire	Overall hospital mortality rate was 3.9. The leading cause of trauma was car accidents and children under 1 year of age were 15% of the total casualties. Trauma remains the major cause of death.
Lieseimer	2011	USA	Early Post-Traumatic Seizures in Moderate to	Cohort Study	Cohort	The primary outcome was seizure activity

			<p>Severe Pediatric Traumatic Brain Injury: Rates, Risk Factors, and Clinical Features</p>			<p>during the first 7 days as determined by clinician observation or EEG analysis. Of the 275 patients included in the study, 34 had identified EPTS (12%). Risk factors identified on bivariable analysis included pre-hospital hypoxia, young age, non-accidental trauma (NAT), severe TBI, impact seizure, and subdural hemorrhage, while receiving an AED was protective. Independent risk factors identified by multivariable analysis were age <2 years (OR 3.0 [95% CI 1.0,8.6]), Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score ≤ 8 (OR 8.7 [95% CI 1.1,67.6]), and NAT as a mechanism of injury (OR 3.4 [95% CI 1.0,11.3]). AED treatment was protective against EPTS</p>
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						(OR 0.2 [95% CI 0.07,0.5]). Twenty-three (68%) patients developed EPTS within the first 12 h post-injury. This early peak in EPTS activity and demonstrated protective effect of AED administration in this cohort suggests that to evaluate the maximal potential benefit among patients at increased risk for EPTS, future research should be randomized and prospective, and should intervene during pre-trauma center care with initiation of continuous EEG monitoring as soon as possible.
Claret Teruela	2007	Spain	Severe head injury among children: computer tomography Evaluation as a prognostic factor.	Retrospective	Questionnaire	In a group of patients, initial Glasgow Coma Scale was related with the initial neuroimaging pattern, and this relation was statistically significant. Findings in the first and second neuroimaging

						were useful as prognostic factors in the series.
Adil H. Haider	2011	USA	Mechanism of injury predicts case fatality and functional outcomes in pediatric trauma patients	Retrospective	Questionnaire	Pediatric pedestrians struck by a motor vehicle have the highest risk of locomotion (OR, 3.30; 95% CI, 2.89-3.77) and expression (OR, 1.65; 95% CI, 1.22-2.23) disabilities. Mechanism of injury is a significant predictor of clinical and functional outcomes at discharge for equivalently injured patients. These findings have implications for injury prevention, staging, and prognosis of traumatic injury and posttreatment planning.
TharaTunthanathip	2021	Thailand	Application of machine learning to predict the outcome of pediatric traumatic brain injury	Cohort	Cohort	Road traffic accident was the most common mechanism of injury, accounting for 68.7%. At hospital discharge, favorable outcomes were achieved in

						<p>97.0% of patients, while the mortality rate was 2.2%. Glasgow coma scale score, hypotension, pupillary light reflex, and subarachnoid hemorrhage were associated with TBI outcomes following traditional binary logistic regression; hence, the 4 prognostic factors were used for building ML models and testing performance. The support vector machine model had the best performance for predicting pediatric TBI outcomes: sensitivity 0.95, specificity 0.60, positive predicted value 0.99, negative predictive value 1.0; accuracy 0.94, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve 0.78.</p>
Grinkevičiūtė	2011	Lithuania	Prognostic factors of Glasgow	Cohort	Cohort	As initial assessment tools the

			<p>outcome scale after six month in children after severe traumatic brain injury.</p>		<p>Glasgow Coma Score (GCS), Pediatric Trauma Score (PTS), Pediatric Index of Mortality 2 (PIM2) were calculated during the first hour after admission. Gender, age, injury mechanism, injury pattern, time until admission, existence of a multiple injuries, findings on initial CT, hematological and circulatory disorders, intracranial pressure (ICP), and cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) were evaluated and their impact on the outcome analyzed. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression was chosen for statistical analysis. The outcome after six months was assessed using Glasgow Outcome Scale (GOS). All children were treated</p>
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						according to the protocol of severe head trauma management. Survival rate was 86%. Outcomes were assessed after six months.
Grant McFadyen	2012	USA	Initial assessment and management of pediatric trauma patients	Descriptive	Descriptive	Early recognition and treatment of life-threatening airway obstruction, inadequate breathing, and intra-abdominal and intra-cranial hemorrhage significantly increases survival rate after major trauma.
Halldorsson	2012	USA	The scope of early traumatic brain injury as a long-term health concern ,prevalence and prognostic factors	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	The scope of TBI as a health concern in adolescence and young adulthood is greater than previously documented. The findings suggest that TBI event-related factors, especially force of impact, have greater predictive value than clinical symptoms of severity at the acute stage, females being more sensitive to the effects of

						mild TBI than males.
M. Piastra	2017	Italy	Clinical Outcomes and Prognostic Factors for Spontaneous Intracerebral Hemorrhage in Pediatric ICU	Retrospective	Questionnaire	Overall PICU mortality was 24.2%. On multivariate analysis, the single factor markedly influencing survival was the presence of midline shift. A low Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) on PICU admission was predictive of severe neurological impairment in survivors. Intraventricular hemorrhage and infratentorial origin did not influence outcome in this series.
Polinder	2005	Holland	Prevalence and Prognostic Factors of Disability After Childhood Injury	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	Most children show fast and complete recovery after injury, but a small subgroup of patients have residual disabilities after 9 months. Girls have a 3-fold risk compared with boys for long-term disability after childhood injury. Prognosis in the long-term is also negatively influenced by

						hospitalization, but in absolute terms, residual disabilities are frequently caused by injuries that are treated fully in the emergency department. The group of injured children with persistent health problems as identified in this study indicates the importance of health monitoring over a longer period in trauma care, whereas trauma care should be targeted at early identification and management of the particular needs of these patients.
Jagannathan	2008	Pittsburgh	34. Long-term outcomes and prognostic factors in pediatric patients with severe traumatic brain injury and elevated intracranial pressure	Cross-sectional descriptive	Questionnaire	Controlling elevated ICP is an important factor in patient survival following severe pediatric TBI. The modality used for ICP control appears to be less important. Long-term follow-up is essential to determine neurocognitive sequelae associated with Traumatic Brain

						Injury
Marius Bläsius	2021	Germany	36. Helicopter Emergency Medical Service and Hospital Treatment Levels Affect Survival in Pediatric Trauma Patients	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	In our national pediatric trauma cohort, both HEMS transportation and treatment in level I trauma centers were independent factors of improved survival in pediatric trauma patients.
Hong Kan	2009	Malaysia	Prognostic Factors of Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Outcome in Children Aged 2-16 Years at A Major Neurosurgical Referral Centre	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	A low coma score upon admission was independently associated with poor outcome. The presence of diabetes insipidus within 3 days post-TBI hyperglycaemia prolonged PT ratio and leukocytosis were associated with poorer outcome. Knowledge of these prognostic factors helps neurosurgeons and neurocritical care specialists to manage and improve outcome in severe TBI in children.
Narci	2009	Turkey	The prognostic	Cross-sectional,	Questionnaire	AIS ⁸ , ISS ⁹ , TRISS ¹⁰ and

⁸ abbreviated injury scale

⁹ injury severity score

¹⁰ trauma score— injury severity score

			importance of trauma scoring systems in pediatric patients.	descriptive		PTS were independent predictors of morbidity AIS and ISS were independent predictors of the length of hospital stay RTS, TRISS, ISS and PTS ¹¹ were independent predictors of the need for ICU. Among laboratory findings, blood glucose, AST and ALT were found to be independent predictors of liver trauma. ISS was found to be more valuable than other trauma scoring systems for prognostic evaluation of pediatric trauma patients. On the other hand, blood glucose, AST, and ALT are easily available, cheap, and valuable alternative laboratory findings in prognostic evaluation.
Mustafa Kamal	2011	KSA	Is the fall of platelets in children with	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	Platelets fall was significantly

¹¹ pediatric trauma score

			TBI valuable?			higher in patients with poor outcomes compared to those with favorable outcomes PF was also closely related to the severity of TBI, GCS score, clinical outcome and length of stay for survivors The frequency of thrombocytopenia was significantly higher in poor outcome patients than in favorable outcome patients.
Temprano	2007	Spain	Intracranial pressure and cerebral perfusion pressure as risk factors in children with traumatic brain injuries.	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	This study showed that patients with initial CPPs between 40 and 70 mm Hg were found to have a better neurological prognosis than those with CPPs either higher or lower than that range.
Chiaretti A	2002	Italy	Prognostic factors and outcomes of children with severe head injury an 8 years' experience.	Cross-sectional, descriptive, retrospective	Questionnaire	In addition to GCS types of trauma and brain lesion, hypoxia and hypotension, hemocoagulative disorders DIC hyperglycemia and early post

						traumatic seizures are predictors of GOS. A knowledge of these prognostic factors and the correct management of children with severe head injury helps clinicians to improve outcome and to reduce morbidity and mortality.
Kipfmueller	2012	Germany	Epidemiology, risk stratification and outcome of severe pediatric trauma.	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	.The most important factor to increase mortality in the severely injured pediatric population is the extent of a concomitant traumatic brain injury (TBI). In addition, the acute trauma-associated coagulopathy, which is triggered multifactorial, is an independent prognostic marker for mortality in severe trauma. The complexity of all currently available trauma-scores for the pediatric population is one reason why these scores are

						not unequivocal recommended for the early use in pediatric trauma care. The pediatric BIG-Score was developed to allow an early prognostic stratification for pediatric trauma patients and includes with base excess (BE), INR (International Normalized Ratio) and GCS (Glasgow Coma Scale) relevant prognostic factors for poor outcome. Early risk stratification is crucial in pediatric trauma due to mortality rates ranging between 9% and 15% and with 50% of all fatalities to occur within the first 24 h of hospital admission.
Randall Board	2021	USA	Long-Term Outcomes after Pediatric Injury: Results of the Assessment of Functional Outcomes and Health-Related	Cross-sectional, descriptive	Questionnaire	Six-month functional status was measured using the Functional Status Scale (FSS) and health-related quality of life using the Pediatric Quality of Life

			Quality of Life after Pediatric Trauma in Children.			Inventory. Increasing levels of impaired discharge FSS score were associated with impaired FSS and lower Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory scores at 6-month follow-up. Additional factors on multivariable analysis associated with 6-month FSS impairment included older age, penetrating injury type, severe head injuries, and spine injuries, and included older age for lower 6-month Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory scores.
Hernández	2021	Spain	Early prognostic factors for morbidity and mortality in severe traumatic brain injury.	Cohort	Questionnaire	Statistical significance was found between the score on the prehospital Glasgow coma scale, pupillary reactivity, arterial hypotension, hypoxia, certain analytical and radiological alterations, such as compression

						of the basal cisterns, with an unfavorable prognosis. The multivariate analysis showed that it is possible to make predictive models of the evolution of the patients. It is possible to identify prognostic factors of poor evolution in the first 24hours after trauma. Knowledge of them can help clinical decision-making as well as offer better information to families.
Theodorou	2021	USA	Causes of early mortality in pediatric trauma patients.	Descriptive, Cross-sectional	Questionnaire	Death from hemorrhage was more common in adolescents. The highest case fatality rates were seen in hangings and gunshot wounds. Half of pediatric trauma deaths occurred within 24 hours. Death from hemorrhage was rare, but all occurred within 6 hours of arrival. This is a critical time for interventions for bleeding

						control to prevent death from hemorrhage in children. Analysis of these deaths can focus efforts on the urgent need for development of new hemorrhage control adjuncts in children.
Yoon	2003	Korea	The Prognostic Factors in Multiple Traumas in Children.			Motor vehicle related injuries caused the majority of the multiple organ injuries the children, with liver injuries accounting for the greatest numbers. The survivals showed differences in relation to age, sex, number of injured organs and PTS. The PTS is an important triage for injured children, but could not reflect the prognosis of the injured patients when the clinical appearances were not reflected.

Results:

After reviewing the abstract and complete text of the articles related to the research topic, the desired information was extracted for writing a review study. The data needed for each study included writer's name, year, place, type of study, sampling method, data collection tool and

conclusions. Finally, the information obtained from the articles was categorized and eventually reported in a form of a review article.

Discussion:

This study was done with the goal of evaluating clinical features and prognostic factors in children with brain trauma admitted in pediatric intensive care unit.

The results show that the most important factor to increase mortality in the severely injured pediatric population is the extent of a concomitant traumatic brain injury (TBI). In addition, the acute trauma-associated coagulopathy, which is triggered multifactorial, is an independent prognostic marker for mortality in severe trauma. The complexity of all currently available trauma-scores for the pediatric population is one reason why these scores are not unequivocal recommended for the early use in pediatric trauma care. The pediatric BIG-Score was developed to allow an early prognostic stratification for pediatric trauma patients and includes with base excess (BE), INR (International Normalized Ratio) and GCS (Glasgow Coma Scale) relevant prognostic factors for poor outcome. Early risk stratification is crucial in pediatric trauma due to mortality rates ranging between 9% and 15% and with 50% of all fatalities to occur within the first 24 h of hospital admission.

Another research shows that fever is an important symptom in children with brain trauma. Treatment or even prevention of fever for patients may improve patient outcomes. Because children with head trauma often have unpredictable outcomes), predicting the prognostic outcomes in clinical settings is somewhat inevitable.

The analysis done by Bahlol shows that the pediatric trauma score (PTS) was low at the admission, the injury severity score (ISS) was high, or the pediatric mortality risk score (PRISM) was also high, meningeal shock, bleeding, or bilateral mydriasis, and serum glucose > 10 mmol / L was associated with mortality. Multivariate analysis showed that the factors with poor prognosis included PRISM > 20 and bilateral mydriasis at the time of admission. Head injury is one of the most common causes of hospitalization and is often followed by road accidents. The short-term prognosis is poor, associated with a high mortality rate (24.3%), and influenced by demographic, clinical, radiological, and biological factors.

Another study shows the rate of mortality in hospital is 3.9. The leading cause of trauma was car accidents and children under 1 year of age were 15% of the total casualties. Trauma remains the major cause of death.

Kate Liesemer found that the primary outcome was seizure activity during the first 7 days as determined by clinician observation or EEG analysis in pediatric patients. Of the 275 patients included in the study, 34 had identified EPTS (12%). Risk factors identified on bivariable analysis included pre-hospital hypoxia, young age, non-accidental trauma (NAT), severe TBI, impact seizure, and subdural hemorrhage, while receiving an AED was protective. Independent risk factors identified by multivariable analysis were age <2 years (OR 3.0 [95% CI 1.0,8.6]), Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score ≤ 8 (OR 8.7 [95% CI 1.1,67.6]), and NAT as a mechanism of injury (OR 3.4 [95% CI 1.0,11.3]). AED treatment was protective against EPTS (OR 0.2 [95% CI 0.07,0.5]). Twenty-three (68%) patients developed EPTS within the first 12 h post-injury. This early peak in EPTS activity and demonstrated protective effect of AED administration in this cohort suggests that to evaluate the maximal potential benefit among patients at increased risk for EPTS, future research should be randomized and

prospective, and should intervene during pre-trauma center care with initiation of continuous EEG monitoring as soon as possible.

In a group of patients, Claret Teruela found that initial Glasgow Coma Scale was related with the initial neuroimaging pattern, and this relation was statistically significant. Findings in the first and second neuroimaging were useful as prognostic factors in the series.

Statistical significance was found between the score on the prehospital Glasgow coma scale in a study conducted by Hernández, pupillary reactivity, arterial hypotension, hypoxia, certain analytical and radiological alterations, such as compression of the basal cisterns, with an unfavorable prognosis. The multivariate analysis showed that it is possible to make predictive models of the evolution of the patients.

It is possible to identify prognostic factors of poor evolution in the first 24 hours after trauma. Knowledge of them can help clinical decision-making as well as offer better information to families.

Analysis done by Dovile Grinkevičiūtė shows, as initial assessment tools the Glasgow Coma Score (GCS), Pediatric Trauma Score (PTS), Pediatric Index of Mortality 2 (PIM2) were calculated during the first hour after admission. Gender, age, injury mechanism, injury pattern, time until admission, existence of a multiple injuries, findings on initial CT, hematological and circulatory disorders, intracranial pressure (ICP), and cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) were evaluated and their impact on the outcome analyzed. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression was chosen for statistical analysis. The outcome after six months was assessed using Glasgow Outcome Scale (GOS). All children were treated according to the protocol of severe head trauma management. Survival rate was 86%. Outcomes were assessed after six months.

Another research revealed that the road traffic accident was the most common mechanism of injury, accounting for 68.7%. At hospital discharge, favorable outcomes were achieved in 97.0% of patients, while the mortality rate was 2.2%. Glasgow coma scale score, hypotension, pupillary light reflex, and subarachnoid hemorrhage were associated with TBI outcomes following traditional binary logistic regression; hence, the 4 prognostic factors were used for building ML models and testing performance. The support vector machine model had the best performance for predicting pediatric TBI outcomes: sensitivity 0.95, specificity 0.60, positive predicted value 0.99, negative predictive value 1.0; accuracy 0.94, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve 0.78.

Findings of Thara Tunthanathip showed the overall PICU mortality was 24.2%. On multivariate analysis, the single factor markedly influencing survival was the presence of midline shift. A low Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) on PICU admission was predictive of severe neurological impairment in survivors. Intraventricular hemorrhage and infratentorial origin did not influence outcome in this series.

Some other investigation found, in addition to GCS types of trauma and brain lesion, hypoxia and hypotension, hemocoagulative disorders DIC hyperglycemia and early post traumatic seizures are predictors of GOS. A knowledge of these prognostic factors and the correct management of children with severe head injury helps clinicians to improve outcome and to reduce morbidity and mortality.

Haider found that the pediatric pedestrians struck by a motor vehicle had the highest risk of locomotion and expression disabilities. Mechanism of injury is a significant predictor of clinical and functional outcomes at discharge for equivalently injured patients. These findings

had implications for injury prevention, staging, and prognosis of traumatic injury and post treatment planning.

After observation of an article written by J Grant McFadyen we found that the early recognition and treatment of life-threatening airway obstruction, inadequate breathing, and intra-abdominal and intra-cranial hemorrhage significantly increases survival rate after major trauma.

Another article showed the scope of TBI as a health concern in adolescence and young adulthood was greater than previously documented. The findings suggest that TBI event-related factors, especially force of impact, had greater predictive value than clinical symptoms of severity at the acute stage, females being more sensitive to the effects of mild TBI than males.

Most children show fast and complete recovery after injury, but a small subgroup of patients have residual disabilities after 9 months. Girls have a 3-fold risk compared with boys for long-term disability after childhood injury. Prognosis in the long-term is also negatively influenced by hospitalization, but in absolute terms, residual disabilities are frequently caused by injuries that are treated fully in the emergency department. The group of injured children with persistent health problems as identified in this study indicates the importance of health monitoring over a longer period in trauma care, whereas trauma care should be targeted at early identification and management of the particular needs of these patients.

Controlling elevated ICP is an important factor in patient survival following severe pediatric TBI. The modality used for ICP control appears to be less important. Long-term follow-up is essential to determine neurocognitive sequelae associated with Traumatic Brain Injury.

Study showed that patients with initial CPPs between 40 and 70 mm Hg were found to have a better neurological prognosis than those with CPPs either higher or lower than that range.

In our national pediatric trauma cohort, both HEMS transportation and treatment in level I trauma centers were independent factors of improved survival in pediatric trauma patients.

AIS, ISS, TRISS and PTS were independent predictors of morbidity AIS and ISS were independent predictors of the length of hospital stay RTS, TRISS, ISS and PTS were independent predictors of the need for ICU. Among laboratory findings, blood glucose, AST and ALT were found to be independent predictors of liver trauma.

ISS was found to be more valuable than other trauma scoring systems for prognostic evaluation of pediatric trauma patients. On the other hand, blood glucose, AST, and ALT are easily available, cheap, and valuable alternative laboratory findings in prognostic evaluation.

A low coma score upon admission was independently associated with poor outcome, knowledge of these prognostic factors helps neurosurgeons and neurocritical care specialists to manage and improve outcome in severe TBI in children.

Platelets fall was significantly higher in patients with poor outcomes compared to those with favorable outcomes PF was also closely related to the severity of TBI, GCS score, clinical outcome and length of stay for survivors The frequency of thrombocytopenia was significantly higher in poor outcome patients than in favorable outcome patients.

Six-month functional status was measured using the Functional Status Scale (FSS) and health-related quality of life using the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory.

Increasing levels of impaired discharge FSS score were associated with impaired FSS and lower Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory scores at 6-month follow-up. Additional factors on multivariable analysis associated with 6-month FSS impairment included older age,

penetrating injury type, severe head injuries, and spine injuries, and included older age for lower 6-month Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory scores.

Motor vehicle related injuries caused the majority of the multiple organ injuries the children, with liver injuries accounting for the greatest numbers. The survivals showed differences in relation to age, sex, number of injured organs and PTS. The PTS is an important triage for injured children, but could not reflect the prognosis of the injured patients when the clinical appearances were not reflected.

Death from hemorrhage was more common in adolescents. The highest case fatality rates were seen in hangings and gunshot wounds.

Half of pediatric trauma deaths occurred within 24 hours. Death from hemorrhage was rare, but all occurred within 6 hours of arrival. This is a critical time for interventions for bleeding control to prevent death from hemorrhage in children. Analysis of these deaths can focus efforts on the urgent need for development of new hemorrhage control adjuncts in children.

According to studies, the leading cause in increased mortality in the pediatric patients is brain trauma and various factors have been mentioned as prognosis and clinical features. These factors include acute coagulation due to trauma, GCS, open overload BE), INR (international normal ratio), fever, demographic, clinical, radiological and biological factors, prehospital hypoxia, young age, Non-accidental trauma, seizures, subdural hemorrhage and receiving anticonvulsant drugs, first and second stage neuroimaging findings, pupil reaction, arterial hypertension, sex, age, mechanism of injury, pattern of injury, admission time, severity of injuries primary CT findings, circulatory disorders, intracranial pressure (ICP), cerebral hypertension (CPP), infant mortality rate (PIM2), serum lactate, subarachnoid hemorrhage, hypotension, type of trauma, type of lesion, Blood coagulation disorders, Hyperglycemia, Primary post-traumatic seizures, Impulse transmission and energy, early diagnosis and treatment of life-threatening cases, high ICP, hypertension, AIS, ISS, TRISS, PTS, AST and ALT, thrombocytopenia, functional status standard score (FSS) were noted, PRISM > 20 and bilateral mydriasis were associated with a poor prognosis at the time of admission. Low pediatric trauma score (PTS) at admission, high injury severity score (ISS) or high child mortality risk score (PRISM), presence of meningeal shock or bleeding, or bilateral mydriasis and serum glucose > 10 mmol / L accompanied by the mortality rate.

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